

S1. Documentation of SEGM links to NHS policy working group and Cass Review.

Individual	Putative role*	Connection to SEGM and broader anti-trans pseudoscience network
Richard Byng	NHS policy working group	<p>Byng is described as a member of “the NHS England working group on Gender Dysphoria” in an April 2022 meeting with the US Department of Health and Human Services, discussing the Cass Review.ⁱ</p> <p>The meeting lists Byng’s affiliation as SEGMⁱ, he spoke at SEGM’s 2024 conferenceⁱⁱ, and he is an advisor to SEGM.ⁱⁱⁱ</p>
Richard Stephens	NHS policy working group	<p>Stephens is described as a member of “the NHS England working group on Gender Dysphoria” in an April 2022 meeting with the US Department of Health and Human Services, discussing the Cass Review.ⁱ</p> <p>The meeting lists Stephens’ affiliation as SEGMⁱ, he spoke at SEGM’s 2024 conferenceⁱⁱ, and he is a co-founder of the abusive anti-trans conversion therapy group Bayswater Support Group.^{iv}</p>
Az Hakeem	NHS policy working group	<p>Hakeem self-declared his involvement in the Cass Review in a YouTube video^v; the Cass Review team clarified to <i>Trans Safety Network</i> that he had been a member of the policy working group.^{vi}</p> <p>Hakeem is an advisor to SEGM’s sister group Genspect (alongside <i>Irreversible Damage</i> author Abigail Shrier)^{vii}, spoke at SEGM’s 2025 conference^{viii}, and on his website has directed viewers to organizations including SEGM and Bayswater Support Group.^{ix}</p>
Riittakerttu Kaltiala	Cass Review advisory board	<p>Kaltiala lists “The Cass Review, member of advisory board” in a paper’s competing interests section^x; this role has also been confirmed by the University of York.^{xi}</p> <p>The paper’s competing interest section also lists “SEGM (Society for Evidence-based Gender Medicine) 2023.”^{xii} She met with the US Department of Health and Human Services alongside SEGM membersⁱ, and has spoken at all SEGM conferences to date, in 2023^{xiii}, 2024ⁱⁱ, and 2025.^{xiiii}</p>
Trilby (Tilly) Langton	Cass Review advisory board; University of York reviews	<p>Langton is a coauthor of the University of York reviews^{xviii}, and has been confirmed as a member of the Cass Review advisory board by the University of York.^{xi}</p> <p>According to reporting, Langton advocated gender-exploratory therapy (a euphemism for conversion therapy) in training materials to NHS England, alongside SEGM advisory board members Anna Hutchinson and Anastasis Spiliadis.^{xiv} She was also scheduled to speak in a preliminary program of the 2024 SEGM conference^{xv}, but not the final version of the program.ⁱⁱ</p>
<p>*Based on public information, assuming “NHS England working group on gender dysphoria” is the policy working group referred to in the Cass Review. It is unclear whether the “advisory board” grew into the “clinical expert group” referred to in the Cass Review, or whether these are separate; a document obtained from NHS by the author, with names redacted, shows that the clinical expert group had more members than are listed in the University of York advisory board document. NHS has not publicly disclosed the members of the policy working group, the clinical expert group, the Cass Review team, or the relationship between the advisory board and the clinical expert group. For what is known about the relevant groups, see supplemental tables S4-S8.</p>		

S2. Documentation for Figure 1 timeline.

Date	Event	Notes
27 Jan 2020 ^{xxv}	SEGM founded	For timeline of the anti-trans network since 2015 (albeit US-centered), see SPLC. ^{xxvii}
30 Jan 2020 ^{xxviii}	Cass to chair NHS policy working group	
30 Jun 2020 ^{xx}	<i>Irreversible Damage: The Transgender Craze Seducing Our Daughters</i>	Written by Abigail Shrier, now an advisor to SEGM's sister group Genspect (alongside NHS policy working group member Az Hakeem). ^{xvii} First edition 30 Jun 2020, Regnery.
22 Sep 2020 ^{xx}	Cass to chair Cass Review	
14 Oct 2020 ^{xxi}	NICE review on puberty blockers	Document completed in October 2020 but not publicly released until March 2021.
21 Oct 2020 ^{xxii}	NICE review on gender-affirming hormones	Document completed in October 2020 but not publicly released until March 2021.
10 Mar 2022 ^{xxiii}	Cass Review interim report	Document dated to February 2022 (no day); publication day reported by MERMAIDS.
05 Apr 2022 ⁱ	SEGM members of NHS meet with HHS	Meeting also included non-NHS individuals affiliated with SEGM such as SEGM founder William Malone, and Cass Review advisor Riittakerttu Kaltiala.
19 Jul 2022 ^{xxiv}	Cass recommends NHS restrict puberty blockers	Included as appendix 6 of Cass Review, final report. The main text of the Review says July 2023; Cass has confirmed that "2023" was a typo (Cass H, <i>pers comm</i>).
08 Mar 2023 ^{xxv}	<i>Mother Jones</i> report on anti-LGBT network	Emails leaked to journalists by the de-transitioner Lisa Shupe and later posted online. <i>Mother Jones</i> focused on legislative efforts including by Rep. Fred Deutsch.
12 Dec 2023 ^{xxvi}	SPLC report on anti-LGBT network	Highly recommended report, including the associated timeline. ^{xxvii}
12 Mar 2024 ^{xxviii}	NHS restricts puberty blockers	
09 Apr 2024 ^{xxix}	York reviews	
10 Apr 2024 ^{xxx}	Cass Review final report	Document dated to April 2024 (no day); publication day reported by MERMAIDS.
29 May 2024 ^{xxxi}	UK emergency ban on puberty blockers	
22 Aug 2024 ^{xxxii}	UK extends ban on puberty blockers	
06 Nov 2024 ^{xxxiii}	UK extends ban on puberty blockers	Second ban extension omitted from figure 1.
03 Sep 2024 ^{xxxiv}	SEGM brief to SCOTUS	SEGM's amicus brief cites the Cass Review.
02 Oct 2024 ⁱⁱ	NHS officials attend SEGM conference	NHS speakers include Michael Absoud, deputy head of upcoming puberty blockers trial; Anastassis Spiliadis, advocate of gender-exploratory therapy (a euphemism for conversion therapy); and Julie Alderson, responsible for a new NHS gender service. Preliminary program also listed Trilby Langton, coauthor of the York reviews, though the final program does not. ^{xv} Program also listed Cass advisor Riittakerttu Kaltiala.
15 Oct 2024 ^{xxxv}	ACPeds brief to SCOTUS	ACPeds' amicus brief cites the Cass Review.
15 Oct 2024 ^{xxxvi}	ADF brief to SCOTUS	ADF's amicus brief cites the Cass Review.
11 Dec 2024 ^{xxxvii}	UK indefinitely bans puberty blockers	Ban also followed a public consultation which included anti-trans activist groups such as Genspect, Transgender Trend, Bayswater Support Group, and LGB Alliance. ^{xxxvi}
18 Jun 2025 ^{xxxviii}	SCOTUS upholds Tennessee ban on puberty blockers	SCOTUS's opinion cites the Cass Review.

S3. Documentation of SEGM founder’s coordination with Christian nationalist groups ADF and ACPeds.*

Date	From:	Email text	Bahry comment
24 Sep 2019	William Malone [founder, SEGM]	<p>Subject: Quillette article: No One is Born in the Wrong Body</p> <p>An essay I wrote with 2 collaborators called “No One is Born in the Wrong Body” was published on Quillette today—please distribute to any who may benefit from reading it. https://quillette.com/2019/09/24/no-one-is-born-in-the-wrong-body/</p>	<p>Recipients included ADF lawyers (Gary McCaleb, Jeff Shafer, Matt Sharp, Roger G. Brooks), current ACPeds members (Andre Van Mol, Paul Hruz, Quentin Van Meter), former ACPeds member Michael Laidlaw, and ACPeds president Michelle Cretella.</p> <p>Additional recipients included, among others, South Dakota Representative Fred Deutsch, who had previously tried to pass “bathroom bills” to block trans people from using bathrooms that match their gender identity, and Paul McHugh, who conspired to shut down the Johns Hopkins sex change clinic in 1979.**</p>
28 Oct 2019	William Malone [founder, SEGM]	<p>Subject: Re: Endocrine Society's Latest Slime</p> <p>James, what Mike said. It might take years, but we’re going to get them.</p> <p>On Oct 28, 2019, at 4:48 PM, Michael Laidlaw wrote:</p> <p>Thanks Jamie. It is an ultimate, long term goal of mine to make sure that the Endocrine Society is embarrassed, publicly humiliated, and sued mercilessly by the many detransitioners and particularly those harmed as children and adolescents by their low to no quality evidence guidelines. [...]</p>	<p>SEGM founder William Malone refers to ACPeds former member Michael Laidlaw as “we,” planning to target the Endocrine Society for its endorsement of endocrine care for trans adolescents.</p>
05 Nov 2019	Michelle Cretella [president, ACPeds]	<p>Subject: Re: Request For A Standards Of Care Document By ACPeds</p> <p>James, Good to hear from you! No need to convince me of the need. Unfortunately, the American College of Pediatricians does not have the bandwidth to do this. However, there is another recently formed group focused solely on this issue that may attempt to draft alternative SOCs. Mike Laidlaw and Will Malone are active within it, I am less so. Let me find out if the group is "out" yet. Best, Michelle</p> <p>On Tue, Nov 5, 2019 at 5:26 PM James Shupe (Formerly Jamie Shupe) [REDACTED] wrote:</p> <p>Hello Dr. Cretella, I wanted to reach out and see if the medical association you are involved with would consider authoring a "standards of care" for people suffering from gender issues? As you well know, WPATH has one, which is going to cause problems for litigants who have been harmed by gender ideology. [...]</p>	<p>ACPeds president Michelle Cretella has advance knowledge that SEGM founder William Malone is forming a group, two months before SEGM was incorporated.</p> <p>Cretella endorses alignment with the strategy of attempting to undermine WPATH’s standards of care, removing a hurdle against anti-transition litigation.</p>
<p>*The emails were leaked to journalists by Lisa Shupe, a trans woman who temporarily identified as a detransitioner, and subsequently posted online. In her time identifying as a detransitioner, Shupe was courted by the network and involved in their strategic litigation efforts. Shupe’s leak, reported on by <i>Mother Jones</i> (focusing on the network)^{xvii} and <i>Xtra</i> (focusing on Shupe)^{xviii}, has been called “a great gift to both the trans community and journalism.”^{xviii}</p> <p>**McHugh promoted a pseudoscientific study by Meyer^{xix}, which used an arbitrary and subjective points scale^{xl} to claim a lack of objective benefit to surgical transition. McHugh later admitted “It was part of my intention, when I arrived in Baltimore in 1975, to help end it”^{xli} due to a view that transition is “collaborating with madness”^{xlii}, and later became a paid expert witness in anti-LGBT litigation.^{xliii} The Cass Review has been compared to these events.^{xliiv}</p>			

S4. Redacted membership of Cass Review team, obtained from NHS England by the author.¹

Dr Hilary Cass	Chair
Section 40	Programme Director
Section 40	Head of Comms and Engagement
Section 40	Head of Policy
Section 40	Project Manager

S5. Redacted membership of policy working group, obtained from NHS England by the author.*

Dr Hilary Cass	Chair; Past President of Royal College of Paediatrics and Child Health
Section 40	Consultant in Paediatric Endocrinology
Section 40	Senior Public Health Adviser
Section 40	Consultant in Paediatric and Adolescent Endocrinology -
Section 40	Professor in Primary Care Research
Section 40	Clinical Psychologist
Section 40	Patient and public voice representative
Section 40	Consultant Clinical Psychologist
Section 40	Consultant Community Paediatrician
Section 40	Professor of Clinical and Biomedical Ethics
Section 40	Professor of Clinical Psychology Research
Section 40	National Head of Safeguarding, NHS England
Section 40	Professor of Evidence-Based Medicine
Section 40	Patient and public voice representative
Section 40	Consultant in Paediatric Endocrinology
Section 40	Consultant Child and Adolescent Psychiatrist
Section 40	Patient and public voice representative
Section 40	Clinical Policy Fellow, NHS England (secretariat)
Section 40	Senior Professional Adviser, NHS Wales

S6. Membership of Cass Review assurance group, available on the Cass Review website.

Member	Current position	Expertise brought
Bobbie Farsides	Professor of Clinical and Biomedical Ethics, Brighton and Sussex Medical School	Clinical and research ethics
Emma Cave	Professor of Healthcare Law, Durham University	Medical law
Faith Gibson	Professor of Child Health and Cancer Care, University of Surrey	Children's nursing and research in children's health
Michael Linney	Retired Paediatrician, RCPCH Registrar 2017 – 2021	Paediatric medicine and governance
Page Nyame-Satterthwaite	Trustee, National Children's Bureau	Children and young people's engagement
Shelley Heard	Past Vice-President, Royal College of Pathologists	Workforce development
Sophie Andrews	Chief Executive, Noah's Ark Children's Hospice	Children's support and advocacy

S7. Membership of Cass Review advisory board, provided by University of York via *WhatDoTheyKnow*.²

Dr Hilary Cass	Chair of Independent Review
Professor Lorna Fraser	Research team
Dr Trilby Langton	Research team
Professor Karl Atkin	Research team
Professor Faith Gibson	Member of assurance group advising Dr Cass
Professor Bobbie Farsides	Member of assurance group advising Dr Cass
Dr Mike Linney	Member of assurance group advising Dr Cass
Professor Riittakerttu Kaltiala	Academic advisor
Professor Thomas Steensma	Academic advisor

¹ Tables S4, S5, and S8 based on the response to a freedom of information request to NHS England by the author. The Review team list was in the body of the response email; for the documents corresponding to S5 and S8 see FOI_pwg.pdf and FOI_ceg.pdf. The original FOI request had reference number FOI-2507-2242742; the response was framed as being a response to a new request with new clarifying information, citing reference number FOI-2508-2251577. The original Jan 2020 announcement of the NHS England policy working group had promised that "We will provide an update on the full membership shortly."^{xviii}

² Table S7 (advisory board) based on the response to a freedom of information request to the University of York, posted at *WhatDoTheyKnow*.^{ix} The included terms of reference state that the advisory board was to guide the commissioned research programme (the York reviews), and that "Additional members may be invited on to the panel as the research progresses." It is uncertain whether the advisory board was distinct from, or grew into, the "clinical expert group."

S8. Redacted membership of Cass Review clinical expert group, obtained by author from NHS England.*

	TITLE	ORGANISATION	Section 40
Dr Hilary Cass	Chair	Independent review of gender identity services for children and young people	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant, Child and Adolescent Psychiatry	NHS England	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Professor of Nursing	Multi-Professional Review group	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Paediatrician	Paediatric Mental Health Association	Section 40
Section 40	Child and Adolescent Psychotherapist	Association of Child Psychotherapists (Child & Adolescent Psychotherapist)	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 General Paediatrics and Adolescent Medicine	Young People's Health Special Interest Group	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Clinical Psychologist	Gender Identity Development Service, Tavistock and Portman NHS Foundation Trust	Section 40
Section 40	Clinical Psychologist and Gender Specialist	Gender Identity Development Service, Tavistock and Portman NHS Foundation Trust	Section 40
Section 40	Clinical Nurse Specialist	University College London Hospitals	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Community Paediatrician	Evelina London, Guy's and St Thomas'	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Child and Adolescent Psychiatrist	Royal Manchester Children's Hospital	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Clinical Psychologist	South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Child and Adolescent Psychiatrist	South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Clinical Psychologist and Neuropsychologist	Association of Clinical Psychologists	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 General Paediatric Consultant	Great Ormond Street Hospital	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 CAMHS	Alder Hey Children's Hospital	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Clinical Psychologist	University Hospital Bristol NHS Trust	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Psychiatrist	Royal College of Psychiatrists	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 GP	RCGP/Primary Care	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 GP	RCGP	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Paediatrician	Sandwell and West Birmingham Hospitals NHS Trust	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Children & Young People's Mental Health	NHS England, Specialised commissioning	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Designated Doctor for Safeguarding and Looked After Children	NNDHP	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Clinical Psychologist	Co-opt for assessment piece	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Consultant Clinical Psychologist	SLAM	Section 40
Section 40	Section 40 Adult Gender Consultant	Co-opt	Section 40
	Education – seeking representation		

*Rather than redacting on a case-by-case basis, it appears likely that entire columns were redacted, and then select pieces unredacted. The redactions even appear to include the column header "Name." For the original document, preserving the original lengths of the redaction blocks, see FOI_ceg.pdf.

Useful resources:

Assigned Media. Trans Data Library. <https://www.assignedmedia.org/trans-data-library>

SPLC. Extremist files: Anti-LGBTQ. <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/extremist-files/anti-lgbtq/>

SPLC. Extremist files: ADF. <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/extremist-files/alliance-defending-freedom/>

SPLC. Extremist files: ACPeds. <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/extremist-files/american-college-pediatricians/>

SPLC. Combatting Anti-LGBT+ Pseudoscience Through Accessible Information Narratives. 12 Dec 2023. <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/reports/captain/>

SPLC. Timeline: Building a pseudoscience network. 12 Dec 2023. <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/reports/timeline-building-pseudoscience-network/>

Lay introduction to ADF:

LastWeekTonight (HBO). Alliance Defending Freedom. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sCAuHH5EYnE>.

ⁱ <https://mobile.reginfo.gov/public/do/viewEO12866Meeting?viewRule=true&rin=0945-AA17&meetingId=131923&acronym=0945-HHS/OCR>

ⁱⁱ https://segm.org/sites/default/files/2025-08/SEGM%20Athens%20agenda_1.pdf

ⁱⁱⁱ https://segm.org/about_us. Accessed 10 Mar 2026.

^{iv} <https://www.thebureauinvestigates.com/stories/2024-07-02/one-day-they-may-thank-us-for-that-abuse-inside-the-bayswater-support-group/>

^v <https://youtu.be/j1-nURL4mlg?si=sGrI4vhhUDI2Z5OO&t=195>

^{vi} <https://transsafety.network/posts/statement-on-nhs-gd-wg/>; *Trans Safety Network*, pers. comm.

^{vii} <https://genspect.org/meet-the-team/advisory-board/>. Accessed 10 Mar 2026.

^{viii} <https://segm.org/sites/default/files/2025-08/Agenda%207.29.2025.pdf>

^{ix} <https://web.archive.org/web/20240327202212/http://www.drazhakeem.com/specialist-psychotherapy-for-gender-dysphoria/>

^x <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjment-2023-300940>

^{xi} https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/cass_review_study_advisory_board#incoming-3330619

^{xii} https://segm.org/NYC_2023

^{xiii} https://adc.bmj.com/content/109/Suppl_2/s73

^{xiv} <https://transsafety.network/posts/gender-exploratory-nhs-training/>

^{xv} <https://www.erininthemorning.com/p/nhs-trans-care-officials-speak-at>

^{xvi} <https://opencorporates.com/filings/642292657>. Accessed 10 Mar 2026.

^{xvii} <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/reports/timeline-building-pseudoscience-network/>

^{xviii} <https://www.england.nhs.uk/2020/01/update-on-gender-identity-development-service-for-children-and-young-people/>

^{xix} <https://www.simonandschuster.com/books/Irreversible-Damage/Abigail-Shrier/9781684510467>. Accessed 10 Mar 2026.

^{xx} <https://www.england.nhs.uk/2020/09/nhs-announces-independent-review-into-gender-identity-services-for-children-and-young-people/>

^{xxi} <https://web.archive.org/web/20210331174945/https://arms.nice.org.uk/resources/hub/1070905/attachment>

^{xxii} <https://web.archive.org/web/20210331202227/https://arms.nice.org.uk/resources/hub/1070871/attachment>

^{xxiii} <https://mermaidsuk.org.uk/news/the-cass-review-interim-report-mermaids-statement/>

^{xxiv} <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/ukgwa/20250310143933/https://cass.independent-review.uk/home/publications/final-report/>

^{xxv} <https://www.motherjones.com/politics/2023/03/anti-trans-transgender-health-care-ban-legislation-bill-minors-children-lgbtq/>

^{xxvi} <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/reports/captain/>

^{xxvii} <https://www.splcenter.org/resources/reports/timeline-building-pseudoscience-network/>

^{xxviii} <https://www.england.nhs.uk/publication/clinical-policy-puberty-suppressing-hormones/>

^{xxix} https://adc.bmj.com/content/109/Suppl_2

^{xxx} <https://mermaidsuk.org.uk/news/the-cass-review-mermaids-response/>

^{xxxi} <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/new-restrictions-on-puberty-blockers>

^{xxxii} <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/puberty-blockers-temporary-ban-extended>

^{xxxiii} <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/extension-to-temporary-ban-on-puberty-blockers>

^{xxxiv} <https://www.scotusblog.com/cases/case-files/united-states-v-skrmetti/>. Accessed 10 Mar 2026.

^{xxxv} <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/ban-on-puberty-blockers-to-be-made-indefinite-on-experts-advice>

^{xxxvi} <https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/proposed-changes-to-the-availability-of-puberty-blockers-for-under-18s/outcome/governments-response-to-the-targeted-consultation-on-proposed-changes-to-the-availability-of-puberty-blockers>

^{xxxvii} <https://xtramagazine.com/power/detransition-terf-movement-elisa-shupe-247592>

^{xxxviii} <https://www.assignedmedia.org/breaking-news/elisa-rae-shupe-complicated-profile-bravery>

^{xxxix} <https://doi.org/10.1001/archpsyc.1979.01780090096010>

^{xl} <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02115944>

^{xli} <https://www.jstor.org/stable/41213388>

^{xlii} <https://firstthings.com/surgical-sex/>

^{xliii} <https://doi.org/10.1017/jme.2023.9>

^{xliiv} <https://www.nytimes.com/2024/08/13/opinion/cass-report-trans-kids.html>